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par

Catherine Annen

Research Fellow
School of Earth Sciences, Université de Bristol

Modelling the growth of Volcanoes, Plutons, and Magma reservoirs

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Composition du jury :

Tim DRUITT - Professeur, Université Blaise Pascal Rapporteur
Katharine CASHMAN - Professeur, Université de Bristol, GB Rapporteur
Caroline MARTELL - Chargée de recherche CNRS, ISTO Orléans Rapporteur
Joachim GOTTSMANN - Reader, Université de Bristol, GB Examineur
Jean-François MOYEN-Professeur, Université de Saint-Etienne Examineur
Thierry MENAND - Maître de conférence, Université Blaise Pascal ... Responsable tuteur

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De la discussion jaillit la lumière

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Chapter 1

Introduction

My first interests as a volcanology student rested in volcanic hazards and risks. In this context, I studied for my master thesis the fumaroles of Vulcano (Aeolian Islands) at the University of Geneva under the supervision of Jean-Jacques Wagner and participated to the measurements of self-potential at Piton de la Fournaise (La Réunion, Indian Ocean) with a team of the *Institut de Physique du Globe of Paris* (IPGP) in order to qualify for a postgraduate Certificate in Assessment and Mitigation of Geological Risk (CERG, University of Geneva).

I started to use numerical simulations and to address fundamental questions on how volcanoes work for my PhD thesis under the supervision of Ariel Provost and Jean-François Lénat at University of Clermont-Ferrand and in co-supervision with the University of Geneva (Jean-Jacques Wagner). I will describe in the next chapter my PhD research on the growth of shield edifices.

Numerical simulation remained my main tool of investigation during the rest of my career. After my PhD, I made a brief come back to volcanic risks with a statistical study of eruptions impact (Annen and Wagner, 2003). Then I became a member of the volcanology group of the University of Bristol, where, under the impulsion of Steve Sparks, I embarked in the modelling of heat transfer and melt generation. Our objective was to quantify the amount of melt produced by partial melting of a crust invaded by mafic intrusions but, to our surprise, I found that the dominant source of silicic melt were the mafic intrusions themselves rather than the crust. This became the basis of a petrogenetic model, the deep hot zone model, that proved very popular in the petrological community.

I later used numerical simulation of magma emplacement and heat transfer computation to investigate a range of problems, including the generation and longevity of magma chambers, magma convection, anatexis and contact aureole size. It led to the initiation of collaborative links with researchers in UK, France and the USA.

In chapter 3, I will pose the basis of thermally modelling repeated magma

intrusions. Chapter 4 is about melt differentiation in deep crustal hot zones and chapter 5 is about the conditions needed for the growth of large magma chambers in the upper crust. These chapters on basic science are followed by two chapters detailing case studies (Fig. 1.1). In chapter 6, the models are used to get insight into the dynamics of two magma chambers that underlay active andesitic volcanoes of the lesser Antilles Arc: Mt Pelee (Martinique) and Soufrière Hills (Montserrat) and in chapter 7 they are applied to the emplacement of two plutons: the Manaslu (Himalaya) and the Adamello (Italian Alps). In chapter 8, I will describe current work and research projects. I will finish the thesis with a conclusion chapter.

Figure 1.1: Locations of case studies referred to in this study. In italics are the case studies that are in progress. Red frames indicate plutons; light blue frames indicate volcanic systems

Chapter 2

The growth of shield volcanoes

I discovered basaltic shield volcanoes when preparing a field-work based thesis to validate my certificate in assessment and management of geological risk (CERG) delivered by the University of Geneva. I was integrated in an team of the *Institut de Physique du Globe de Paris* (IPGP) measuring self-potential at Piton de la Fournaise (Réunion Island, Indian Ocean, fig 1.1). The data collected during six weeks in the field resulted in a self-potential map of the volcano. A large positive anomaly is attributed to a hydrothermal system, with a source at 2 km, which shape reflects the shape of the underlying magmatic system (Zlotnicki et al, 1994).

The objective of my PhD thesis was to use numerical simulation to explore the growth mechanisms of shield volcanoes. I quantified the respective roles of edifice bulging caused by dykes' intrusion (endogenous growth) and of edifice construction by lava flows accumulation (exogenous growth). Following Martel et al (1993), the effect of dykes was calculated with the analytical solution of Okada (1985) that gives surface displacements caused by the opening of a tensile fault. We assumed that the displacement caused by a dyke is similar to the displacement caused by a tensile fault. The lava flows were modelled as the flow of a Bingham fluid. The models showed that endogenous growth is significant and can contribute to 30% of an edifice height and that dykes orientations and dimensions control the edifice shape.

The model was applied to the now largely eroded Koolau volcano (O'ahu Island, Hawai'i, fig. 2.1). The core of Koolau edifice is formed by dykes that were systematically described by Walker (1986). I used these data of dykes dimension and orientation, and lava flow characteristics from Kilauea (Hawai'i), a similar but active volcano, to reconstruct the Koolau edifice before erosion. This modelled edifice is very close to the edifice morphology obtained by extrapolation of its slope, providing a positive test of the validity of the volcano growth model (Annen et al., 2001).

A question this study aimed to answer was why the cone of Piton de la Four-

naise is elongated in an East-West direction despite the fact that dykes are preferentially oriented in a North-South direction (fig. 2.2). Modelling showed that the orientation of edifice elongation depends on the ratio between dykes length along strike and dikes depth. If the dykes source is deep relative to dykes length, the edifice orientation is perpendicular to the dykes orientation, unless the lava flows are numerous enough to counteract this effect. We were able to reproduce the shape of Piton de la Fournaise and to account for its unusually steep flanks with intrusion of 10000 short, thick dykes sourced at shallow depth, which less than 10% are feeding a lava flow.

Figure 2.1: Eroded Koolau edifice. The edifice elongation is parallel to main dykes orientation. Picture credit: NASA Earth Observatory

Figure 2.2: Piton de la Fournaise. The edifice is slightly elongated E-W, perpendicular to the main dyke orientation marked by rift zones.

The characteristic shape of shield volcanoes with their gentle slopes is generally attributed to the low viscosity of basaltic lava flows. What my PhD showed is that lava flows rheology and volumes, although influential, are only part of the story. Dykes are also affecting volcano growth in two ways: Feeder dykes orientation and dimension control the spatial distribution of lava flows and dyke complexes at the core of volcanoes, by adding volumes to edifices, contribute to their size and morphology.

Selected publication

Annen, C., Lenat, J.F. and Provost, A., 2001. The long-term growth of volcanic edifices: numerical modelling of the role of dyke intrusion and lava-flow emplacement. *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, 105(4): 263-289.

Chapter 3

Modelling of heat transfer between magma and country rock

At the interface between petrology and volcanology is the field of magma chamber and reservoirs dynamics. Because they cannot be directly observed, our knowledge of magma chambers and melt reservoirs is by necessity indirect and derives from the study of eroded igneous bodies, plutonic and volcanic rocks chemistry and petrography, geophysical measurements, and modelling. Since 2000, I have been developing codes to numerically simulate the thermal effect of magma emplacement within the crust. These codes were applied to a range of geological problems and were systematically developed and modified to be applicable to the question I was trying to answer. In comparison with using commercial softwares, the strength of this approach is the flexibility it provides in term of the data that can be produced and the hypothesis that can be tested.

The basic principle of all the simulations is an array of cells to which are attributed compositions, physical properties, temperatures and melt fractions. To simulate an intrusion, magmatic temperatures and high melt fractions are attributed to some of these cells and heat transfer is computed over the array.

At the base of the calculation of heat transfer is the Fourier equation:

$$\rho c \frac{\delta T}{\delta t} + \rho L \frac{\delta X}{\delta t} = k \nabla^2 T \quad (3.1)$$

with ρ , density, c , specific heat, T , temperature, L , latent heat of crystallisation or melting, X , melt fraction, and k thermal conductivity.

Equation (3.1) is solved numerically with finite differences. If the intrusions are high aspect ratio sheets and if volumes are not important to our problem, a one dimensional system can be used and the finite difference equation is:

$$\rho c \frac{T_i^{p+1} - T_i^p}{dt} + \rho L \frac{X_i^{p+1} - X_i^p}{dt} = k \frac{T_{i+1}^p - T_i^p}{dx} - \frac{T_{i-1}^p - T_i^p}{dx} \quad (3.2)$$

Subscript i is the position on the numerical grid. Superscript p is the position in time. dt is the numerical time step and dx is the distance between two points on the numerical grid (Fig. 3.1). For the code to be stable, the condition $dt < K/2dx^2$ must be respected, with K the thermal diffusivity and $K = k/\rho c$. The use of a 1D system is justified for sheet intrusions because the heat loss is mainly through the walls of the intrusion and the heat loss at their tips can be neglected as long as we are not interested in the temperature evolution close to these tips. One dimensional numerical solutions were used to model deep hot zones (Annen and Sparks, 2002, Annen et al., 2006a, Annen et al, 2008a, Melekhova et al., 2013), the emplacement of Manaslu leucogranites (Annen et al., 2006b, Annen and Scaillet, 2006) and the generation of Snake River Plain Rhyolites (Leeman et al, 2008). The results are described in chapter 4 and 7.

To calculate volumes of magma and melts, computation of heat transfer in the three dimensions of space is required. However, full 3D simulations are extremely computer demanding. A way around this problem is to assume a cylindrical symmetry of the intrusions, which is a reasonable assumption for sills especially when considering that the intrusion shape is rarely known in details. The use of cylindrical coordinates allows us to reduce the problem to two dimensions without neglecting heat transfer in the third dimension. The finite difference expression of equation (3.1) in a two dimensional system (Fig. 3.2) and cylindrical coordinates is:

$$\rho c \frac{T_{i,j}^{p+1} - T_{i,j}^p}{dt} + \rho L \frac{X_{i,j}^{p+1} - X_{i,j}^p}{dt} = \frac{k}{r dr} \left[(T_{i-1,j}^p - T_{i,j}^p) \left(r - \frac{dr}{2} \right) + (T_{i+1,j}^p - T_{i,j}^p) \left(r + \frac{dr}{2} \right) + (T_{i,j-1}^p - T_{i,j}^p) r + (T_{i,j+1}^p - T_{i,j}^p) r \right] \quad (3.3)$$

Subscripts i and j give the position in the two dimensions of space. r is the radial distance to the symmetry axis and dr is the distance between two points on the numerical grid. The stability condition is $dt < K/4dr^2$. This solution has been used to estimate how volumes of magma and melt evolve during the growth of an igneous body in Annen et al. (2008b), Annen (2009), Carrichi et al. (2012), Paulatto et al. (2012), Schöpa and Annen (2013) and Annen et al. (2014). The results are described in chapter 5 and 6.

Figure 3.1: One-dimension numerical grid

Figure 3.2: Two-dimensions axisymmetric numerical grid

3.1 Calculating melt fractions

Equations (3.2) and (3.3) contain two unknowns: temperature T^{p+1} and melt fraction X^{p+1} . Melt fraction X depends on T , thus if a derivable function of $X(T)$ is known equations (3.2) and (3.3) can be solved. Approximating $X - T$ relationship with a derivable function is the approach adopted for example by Petford and Gallagher (2001) or Nabelek et al (2012) and is a reasonable solution if the focus is on temperatures evolution. However, if the focus is more on the evolution of melt fractions or melt compositions, a more realistic $X - T$ relationship may be desirable. My codes use data that have been acquired with petrological experiments and linearly extrapolate between data points.

First versions of the code were solving (3.2) and (3.3) iteratively. Following Dufek and Bergantz (2005) and Solano et al (2012), I eventually adopted a method that gives the same results but is more elegant and computer efficient. The heat equation is solved for enthalpy H instead of temperatures and melt fractions, with:

$$H = \rho c T + \rho L X \quad (3.4)$$

so that equation (3.1) becomes:

$$\frac{\delta H}{\delta t} = k \nabla T \quad (3.5)$$

and the right hand side of equations (3.2) and (3.3) is replaced by $\frac{H_{i,j}^{p+1} - H_{i,j}^p}{dt}$.

H is calculated for the temperature and melt fraction of experimental data points with equation (3.4), so that temperatures and melt fractions are easily recovered for any H by interpolation between those data points.

H can also be used to test the code. Because of the law of energy conservation, the sum of enthalpies $\sum A_{i,j} H_{i,j}^p$ over the numerical domain must remain constant over time if the boundaries of the domain are insulated, with $A_{i,j}$ the area of cell at position i, j .

3.2 Initial conditions: the geothermal gradient

Solving equations (3.2) and (3.3) requires initial and boundary conditions. The initial condition is a geothermal gradient. If the initial geothermal gradient is constant with depth, the initial temperatures in the system are this geothermal gradient multiplied by depth. Adopting a constant geothermal gradient is equivalent to assuming that heat production within the crust can be neglected. A more realistic geothermal gradient that decreases with depth can be calculated if the heat production by radiogenic element can be estimated (Fig 3.3). For a two layers crust the initial temperatures are:

$$T_u(z) = \frac{q_0}{k_u} z - \frac{A_u}{2k_u} z^2 \quad (3.6)$$

T_u is upper layer temperature, q_0 is surface heat flow, z is depth, A_u is heat production in the upper layer and k_u is upper layer conductivity.

$$T_l(z) = T_1 + \frac{q_1}{k_l} (z - z_1) - \frac{A_l}{2k_l} (z - z_1)^2 \quad (3.7)$$

T_l is lower layer temperature, q_1 is the heat flow through the interface between the upper and lower layer, z_1 is the depth of the interface, A_l is heat production in the lower layer and k_l is lower layer conductivity.

$$q_1 = q_0 - A_u z_1 \quad (3.8)$$

$$T_1 = \frac{q_0}{k_u} z_1 - \frac{A_u}{2k_u} z_1^2 \quad (3.9)$$

Close to the surface the temperatures determined by a constant geothermal gradient are similar to those calculated with equations (3.6) to (3.9) (Fig. 3.3).

Figure 3.3: Initial temperatures: the dashed line shows a linear geothermal gradient of $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{km}$. The plain line is a more realistic geothermal gradient calculated with equations (3.6) to (3.9) and $q_0 = 50\text{mW}^2$, $A_u = 6.5 \times 10^{-7}\text{W}/\text{m}^3$, $A_l = 4.9 \times 10^{-7}\text{W}/\text{m}^3$, $k = 2.5\text{W}/\text{mK}$. The horizontal line marks the limit between the upper and lower crust.

Thus for the modelling of shallow igneous bodies emplaced at depth of 5 to 10 km, using a constant geothermal gradient is justified.

3.3 Boundary conditions

In the simulations, the upper boundary conditions is a fixed temperature of 0 or 20°C at the Earth's surface. If the numerical domain does not extend to the surface, a heat flux is calculated:

$$q_u = k \frac{(T_s - T_u)}{z_u} \quad (3.10)$$

with T_u the temperature at the upper boundary of the numerical domain, T_s the surface temperature and z_u the distance between the upper boundary and the surface.

For the lower boundary condition, a heat flux q_l is calculated by assuming a magmatic temperature T_m at a given depth outside the numerical domain (Jaupart, personal communication):

$$q_l = k \frac{(T_l - T_m)}{z_l} \quad (3.11)$$

with T_l the temperature at the lower boundary of the numerical domain and z_l the distance between the lower boundary and the depth at which we assume the temperatures are magmatic. Note that neither q_l nor T_l is fixed.

For two-dimensional systems, calculations are done in a half space (Fig. 3.4). One of the vertical boundaries is a symmetry plane with no heat flux through it since the temperatures on both sides of a symmetry plane are by definition identical. We also assume a no heat-flow boundary for the second vertical boundary that is far away from the intrusions. The size of the numerical domain is set to be large enough for the thermal perturbation induced by the intrusions not to reach this boundary over the duration of the simulation.

Figure 3.4: Numerical setup and boundary conditions: the cells at the top of the numerical domain (light grey) are set to a constant temperature equal to the surface temperature. Alternatively, a heat flux through the upper boundary is calculated with equation (3.10). The heat flux through the right and left boundary of the domain is set to 0. The heat flux through the lower boundary is calculated with equation (3.11). To model the emplacement of magma the corresponding cells (red) are set to magma temperatures T_m .

3.4 Intrusions orientation and geometry

The simulations, whose results are presented in the next chapters, involve repeated intrusions. In most cases, the intrusions were horizontal sheet intrusions. I call them sills although I am aware that strictly speaking sills must be concordant with lithological layers. In models of deep hot zone (chapter 4), when the intrusions are emplaced at the mantle-lower crust boundary or at the lower-upper crust boundaries, they are sills *sensu stricto*. I also developed models where intrusions are randomly emplaced in the lower crust or are emplaced in the upper crust but the location of the intrusions does not explicitly correspond to an interface (chapter 5 and chapter 6), i.e. the physical properties of the rocks at the roof and at the floor of the intrusion are identical. I nevertheless call these intrusion sills to convey the message that they are horizontal and in nature they are most probably emplaced at an interface.

According to field observations, analogue experiments and theoretical analysis, dykes tend to convert into sills at the boundary between two lithological layers. If the interface between the two layers is weak, the magma intrudes preferentially along this interface (Kavanagh and Pavier, 2014). If the upper layer is more rigid than the lower layer, a dyke may have difficulties propagating vertically through the upper layer and tend to spread horizontally instead (Kavanagh et al, 2006) (Fig. 3.5). A change in orientation of stress can also result in a dyke converting into a sill (Gudmundsson, 2011). Similarly, a thick layer of rock which density is lower than the magma would force a dyke to propagate horizontally rather than vertically (Taisne and Jaupart, 2009). A recent experimental study shows that a dyke ability to convert into a sill also depends on its solidification (Chanceaux and Menand, 2014). Whatever the physics behind sill propagation, a repetition of the process leads to the growth of an igneous body (Menand, 2008).

Figure 3.5: Analogue experiments: Dyke turning into a sill that propagates at the interface between two layers of gelatine with contrasting rigidities. From Kavanagh et al (2006).

Different ways of emplacing sill intrusions relative to each other have been numerically simulated (Fig. 3.6):

1. Over-accretion, where each sill is emplaced above the former one. One example of over-accretion in nature is the mafic complex beneath Torres del Paine granites (Leuthold et al, 2012).
2. Under-accretion, where each sill is emplaced below the former one. In granitoids, rocks are usually younger at the floor relative to the roof indicating under-accretion. For example, the Torres del Paine granites are emplaced by under-accretion (Michel et al., 2008, Leuthold et al., 2012).
3. Intra-accretion, where each intrusion is emplaced in the middle of the former one. We expect this mode of emplacement to happen if the core of the intrusion is still partially molten, when the next intrusion is emplaced. This emplacement mode is often observed in dykes and when repeated dyke intrusions are modelled I chose this emplacement mode (Annen et al., 2008b).
4. Random emplacement. In this case, the emplacement of an intrusion is not influenced by the location of the former one. To simulate this emplacement mode for sills, the code chooses randomly the intrusion depth within a crust section. This emplacement mode results in pieces of crust to be surrounded by intrusions.

Figure 3.6: Illustration of emplacement modes for sills. Numbers indicate the sequence of emplacement. Sill 1 is the first injected (oldest) and sill 5 is the last injected (youngest)

The emplacement mode is important when crustal melting is modelled (section 4.2). Crustal melting is favoured when large areas of crust are in contact with hot basalt. Sills' random emplacement in a section of crust is most favourable to crust melting. If the basalt underplates the crust, over-accretion, with new hot sills at the contact with the crust, is much more favourable to crust melting than under-accretion where new hot sills are at the contact with the mantle.

3.5 Thermal conductivity

Thermal conductivity is an important parameter that controls the rate of heat loss. A rock thermal conductivity depends on the proportion and conductivity of its constitutive minerals (Robertson, 1988). For example, the conductivity of quartz is five times the conductivity of plagioclase. Conductivities also depend on temperatures. In the range of temperature we are interested in, i.e. between 0°C and magmatic temperatures, conductivities decrease as temperatures increase, so that the country rocks that surround intrusions become more insulating with time as their temperatures increase (Robertson, 1988, Whittington et al, 2009, Chapman and Furlong, 1992, Nabelek et al 2012).

In the simulations ran before 2009, the conductivity was varied as a function of depth and temperature according to Chapman and Furlong (1992):

$$k = k_0 \frac{1 + 1.5z}{1 + 0.0015T} \quad (3.12)$$

with k_0 the conductivity at ambient pressure and temperature, z , the depth and T , the temperature in °C.

Eventually, I also used Whittington et al. (2009) temperature-dependant crustal diffusivities:

$$\kappa(T) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{567.3}{T+273.15} - 0.062\right) \times 10^{-6} & \text{if } T < 572.85^\circ\text{C}; \\ [0.732 - 0.000135(T + 273.15)] \times 10^{-6} & \text{if } T > 572.85^\circ\text{C}; \end{cases} \quad (3.13)$$

and k is equal to $\kappa\rho c$. Heat capacity c is theoretically also temperature dependant but varying c with temperature poses numerical problem as the assumption that H in equation (3.5) is conserved over the system is not respected with a varying heat capacity, thus ρ and c were kept constant and only the thermal conductivities and diffusivities were allowed to vary. Equation (3.13) gives the diffusivity in an average crust and cannot account for the conductivity of a particular rock. In some simulations, as the modelling of Manaslu (chapter 7), I used temperature-invariant conductivities and diffusivities, but systematically varied those conductivities to assess their influence on the results.

3.6 The role of convection

Crystals-poor magma layers of more than a few tens meters are expected to convect. The effect of convection is to homogenise the temperature within the convecting layer and increase the heat flux between the magma and the country rock. If the melting point of the country rock is lower than the intrusion temperature, it might melt and also convect, a process described in Huppert and Sparks (1988). If the country rock does not reach a temperature high enough to convect, the temperature at the intrusion-country rock interface increases rapidly to become very close to the intrusion temperature (Worster et al., 1990). The cooling of the magma layer is then controlled by the country rock capacity to conduct away the excess heat. A convecting magma layer as modelled by Worster et al. (1990) takes half the time to crystallise than a magma layer that cools by conduction only.

When simulating the growth of magma bodies over timescales of tens thousand to millions of year, an explicit simulation of magma convection is not feasible because of its complexity. I nevertheless tried to include in some of the simulations the effect of convection. The most straightforward way to do so is to increase conductivity in equations (3.1) to (3.3) and (3.5) by a factor that corresponds to the Nusselt number. Another approach is to instantaneously homogenise the temperature and melt fraction in the convecting layer (Annen et al., 2008b). To model the magma chamber beneath Soufrière Hills, Montserrat, (chapter 6), we used an even more radical approach by setting all the temperatures above a critical temperature that corresponds to a melt fraction of 0.35 to this critical temperature and transferring the excess heat to the roof of the intrusion (Fig 3.7, Annen et al., 2014). This is equivalent to assuming an extremely efficient convection. Whatever the method adopted, I always found that, on the timescale of a magma body growth, including the effect of convection was not significantly modifying the results. This is because only a small portion of an incrementally growing body is susceptible to convect and the contrast in temperature between the convecting magma and its environment is low. Thus, as stated above, the thermal evolution of the magma body is mostly controlled by conduction through the country rock rather than the mode of heat transfer within the magma.

Figure 3.7: Modelling of Soufrière Hills magma chamber (see section 6.2). *a.* The effect of convection is neglected. *b.* The effect of convection is modelled by instantaneously transferring the heat in excess of temperature = 850°C melt fraction = 0.35 to the adjacent cells.

Chapter 4

Generation of differentiated melts

4.1 The deep crustal hot zone model

Primitive magmas are generated by partial melting of the mantle, but most igneous rocks forming the crust, intrusive or eruptive, are not primitive and are depleted in mafic elements relative to silica and alkali. Differentiation of magma participates to the growth of the continental crust, which has an average andesitic composition, and can be generally divided into a mafic lower crust and a more silica-rich upper crust (Christensen and Mooney, 1995, Rudnick and Fountain, 1995).

Several theories have been proposed to explain the generation of intermediate and silicic magmas. Many petrogenetic models imply differentiation of primitive magma in large shallow magma chambers where a silicic melt separates from more mafic crystals during cooling and crystallization. However, there are two main problems with differentiating mafic magma in the upper crust: a mass balance problem and a thermal problem.

At upper crustal pressure, more than 50% of a basaltic magma has to crystallise before the residual melt enters the field of dacite (Sisson and Grove, 1993). Thus producing granitoid melts requires the simultaneous production of mafic cumulates, whose volumes exceed the volumes of the granitoids. In other words, in situ differentiation to upper crustal composition requires the disposal of huge volume of mafic by-product. Glazner (1994) proposed that dense mafic rocks might sink through the crust until they reach a level of similar density. Another possibility is that differentiation mostly operates in the lower crust in the first place.

The other issue with shallow differentiation is that, because the upper crust is cold, magma solidifies rapidly and must be emplaced at high rates for large magma chambers to form at shallow level (see chapter 5). However, high precision geochronological techniques shows that granitoids plutons are emplaced in the upper crust slowly and incrementally (e.g. Coleman et al, 2014, de Saint Blanquat et

al, 2011, Matzel et al, 2006, Michel et al., 2008, Leuthold et al, 2012), which means that they can not form the big magma tanks required for large-scale differentiation (see chapter 5).

Seismic data (Fig. 4.1, De Bari and Greene, 2012) and outcrops of lower crustal rocks (Fig. 4.2, Schaltegger and Brack, 2007) indicate the presence of large volumes of mafic magmas in the lower crust, commonly at the mantle-lower crust boundary (Fig. 4.1). Layering in seismic profiles (e.g. Wenzel and Brun, 1991) and cyclic variations of sea level (MacLennan and Lovell, 2002) suggest that primitive magmas are injected in the deep crust as sills.

Figure 4.1: Lithological section of four accreted arcs showing the presence of mafic and ultramafic igneous rocks in the lower part of the crust. From de Bari et al and Green (2012)

Based on numerical simulation of the repeated injection of mafic sills, we proposed the following model for the generation of silicic melts (Annen et al., 2006a, fig 4.3):

Mafic magmas produced by partial melting of the mantle are emplaced as sills at the mantle-lower crust boundary (underplating) or within the lower crust. The first emplaced sills solidify and transfer their heat to their surrounding. The temperatures in the crust increase with time as more sills are injected and each successive sill thermally equilibrates at a progressively higher temperature. When this equilibration temperature exceeds solidus, new sills do not completely solidify and melt starts to accumulate. Depending on the fertility of the crust and the

Figure 4.2: Reconstruction of Permian crust of Ivrea Verbano zone, based on field observation and geochemical studies. From Schaltegger and Brack, 2007

locus of magma injection, the crust at the contact with the sills may also partially melt (section 4.2). In this case, and if the crustal melts and the residual melts from sills crystallisation are able to mix, a MASH zone (Melting, Assimilation, Storage and Homogenization) may develop (Hildreth and Moorbath, 1988).

The melt that is residual from basalt crystallisation is hydrous because at high pressure H_2O concentrates in the residual melt. As a consequence, melts density and viscosity are low and the melt is buoyant and relatively easy to extract and mobilise (Annen et al, 2006a, Melkhova et al, 2013). As the melt ascents, it becomes superheated and any entrained minerals are resorbed. As the pressure decreases, the melt capacity to dissolve H_2O decreases and the melt starts to degas when it becomes oversaturated. The melt continues its ascent until it hits the liquidus and starts crystallising. The appearance of crystals dramatically increases the viscosity of the melt, which slows down and eventually stalls when crystal fractions reach a critical value of 40-60%. In this case, crystallisation is first driven by decompression and only after the magma has stopped does cooling take control. An implication of this model is that the magma might never have been on the liquidus at the pressure where solidification is completed.

The arrest of the ascending magma can be due the presence of a rigidity, density or stress barrier (Menand, 2008, Taisne and Jaupart, 2009, Gudmundsson, 2011).

This process may be repeated several times with several levels of accumulation, differentiation, segregation and extraction within the crust. Indeed, in several volcanic areas, the presence of multiple magma reservoirs have been inferred from geodesic, seismic, or petrological data (Elsworth et al, 2008, Dahren et al, 2012, Koulakov et al, 2011).

4.2 Melting the crust

A very popular model of silicic melt generation is by melting of the crust. Granitoids have been divided into S-type, I-type and A-types depending on the composition of the protolith (Chappel and White, 1984, Clemens, 2003). "S" stands for sedimentary and supracrustal and S-type granites are believed to be produced by melting of sediments in the upper parts of the crust. "I" stands for igneous and infracrustal with I-type granite resulting from the melting of igneous rocks in the lower crust. "A" stands for alkaline and anorogenic but the origin of these rare granites is much more controversial. Several theories have been formulated regarding the genesis of "A" granites including the deep melting of depleted granulitic protoliths (e.g. Collins et al, 1982).

Melting of the crust requires a source of heat. Except for some leucogranites that are linked to crustal thickening (England and Thomson, 1984) and possibly shear heating (England et al, 1992), mafic magma is believed to be the source of heat that melts the crust. In particular, calc-alkaline granites are attributed to underplating of mafic magma and re-melting of former basaltic intrusives (e.g. Petford et al, 1996). Indeed, mafic magma is quasi omnipresent in association with differentiated rocks as enclaves or dykes.

I used numerical simulation to quantify the amount of melt produced when basalt sills are intruded at the contact with crusts of various compositions (Annen and Sparks, 2002, Annen et al, 2008a). Specifically, I tested if I-type granites could be produced by partial melting of an amphibolitic crust, S-type granites by partial melting of a pelitic crust and A-type granites by partial melting of a granulitic crust. The amount of crustal melt produced depends strongly on the fertility of the protolith (Fig. 4.4 and 4.5) and on the emplacement mode of basalt sills (See chapter 3, section 3.4). More crustal melts are produced if sills are randomly emplaced within the crust, although a longer incubation time is required between the emplacement of the first basalt sills and the production of crustal melts. If basalt sills are emplaced at the mantle-lower crust boundary (underplating) over-accretion is much more efficient than under-accretion in terms of crustal melt production.

Because basalt is needed as a heat source, the generation of crustal melts is always concomitant with the generation of residual melts from basalt differentiation.

Figure 4.3: Conceptual model of a deep crustal hot zone. From Annen et al (2006).

Figure 4.4: Temperature-melt fraction curves used to numerically simulate melt generation in deep hot zones by fractionation of basalt and melting of the crust. The solidus of the basalt is lower than the solidus of the crust (pelite or amphibolite) because of the presence of H_2O dissolved in the melt. From Annen et al, 2008a.

Crustal and residual melts do not accumulate at the same rate. Accumulation of crustal melt is controlled by heat diffusion through the crust whereas the accumulation of residual melt is controlled by the basalt averaged emplacement rate, i.e. by the sills thickness divided by the time interval between sills emplacement. Over time, the proportion of crustal melts relative to residual melts increases, reaches a maximum and eventually decreases (Fig. 4.6). These proportions depend on the relative fertility of the basalt and the crust. The injection of a dry, hot magma can result in the generation of high amount of melts if the crust is pelitic or amphibolitic, but a wet magma, typical of arc setting, is not expected to be hot enough to produce much melting from an amphibolitic crust. The difference in fertility between the basalt and a mafic crust is due to different contents in H_2O . In an amphibolitic crust the only H_2O available is bound in the structure of hydrated minerals, i.e. mainly in amphiboles. The breakdown temperature of amphibole must be reached to produce significant amount of melts. In contrast, in the crystallising, hydrous basalt, H_2O concentrates in the residual melt and the solidus is at low temperatures (Fig. 4.4).

According to my calculations, large volumes of S-type melts can be produced by partial melting of a fertile pelitic crust. However, my simulations as well as those performed by Petford and Gallagher (2003) and by Dufek and Bergantz

Figure 4.5: Temperature evolution in a deep hot zones where sills of basalts are emplaced by over-accretion at an average rate of 5 mm/yr. More time and more basalts are needed to reach the solidus of an amphibolitic crust relative to a pelitic crust.

Figure 4.6: Ratio of the thickness of crustal melt to residual melt from basalt in a deep hot zone for emplacement modes by over-accretion and by under-accretion. Basalt emplacement rate is 5 mm/yr. The basalt contains 2.5 wt% H_2O . a. The crust is a mafic granulite. b. The crust is an amphibolite. c. The crust is a pelite. Note the change in Y axis scale.

(2005), show that the partial melting of an amphibolitic crust is limited. In an arc environment, the dominant process that produces calc-alkaline (I-type) evolved melt is probably the fractionation of a primitive basalt, rather than crust melting. The generation of A-type granites by melting of a granulitic crust is severely limited by the high melting temperature of an anhydrous protolith. In all calculations, even those involving dry and hot basalt and an emplacement favourable to crust melting, the amount of melt generated by partial melting of a granulitic crust is always insignificant compared to the amount of melt generated by crystallisation of the basalt. This result suggests that other models of A-type melt generation, for example the differentiation of an alkaline mafic magma (e.g. Bonin, 2004), are more plausible.

All these calculations neglect the possible transfer of H_2O from basalt to the crust and its possible role in lowering the crust solidus. This transfer can only be significant in the early stage of the hot zone development because at high pressure saturation degassing of the basalt requires a lot of crystallisation. As soon as the temperatures of the hot zone are high enough for the basalt to retain enough melt to keep H_2O dissolved, any flux melting would cease.

4.3 Composition of residual melts

To gain further insights in the composition of residual melts from basalt crystallisation, new data obtained with experimental petrology were used in the simulation of deep hot zones. The experiments were done by Elena Melekhova at the University of Bristol on primitive basalts from the Island of St Vincent (Lesser Antilles). A very interesting result of her experiments is the role of starting product H_2O content on the crystallisation curves (Fig. 4.7). For a dry basalt (0.3 wt% H_2O), most crystallisation happens over a very narrow temperature range (60 % crystallisation over 20 °C). For a wet basalt (4.5 wt% H_2O), the crystallisation-temperature relationship is almost linear and crystallisation requires a wide temperature range (60 % crystallisation over 200°C). A basalt with 2.3 wt% H_2O exhibits an intermediate behaviour.

A growing deep hot zone is characterised by gradients in temperature. Non-linearity between temperatures and melt fractions (Fig. 4.7) results in multimodalities in term of melt fractions (Fig. 4.8). Shortly after the emplacement of a sill, two types of melt coexist; a lower temperature melt, which has thermally equilibrated with its surrounding and a higher temperature melt in the last emplaced magma pulse, which has not yet equilibrated (Fig. 4.8). In addition, compositional gaps within the thermally equilibrated melt appear in the case of dry and damp parent basalts because of the crystallisation-temperature curve shape. In contrast, a wet magma is more favourable to the production of intermediate com-

positions. The whole hot zone evolves with time towards higher temperatures and melt fractions, which result in a reduction in compositional gaps.

Figure 4.7: Relation between temperatures and melt fractions for equilibrium crystallisation of a basalt at 0.7, 1.0, and 1.3 GPa for different initial H₂O contents. From Melekhova et al., 2013.

Figure 4.8: Simulation of the growth of a deep hot zone by over-accretion of basalt with 2.3 wt% H₂O at a rate of 5 mm/yr. Left: profile of melt fraction. The spike corresponds to the last emplaced sill. The dashed horizontal lines mark the upper and lower limit of the intrusive complex. Right: Kernel distribution of melt fraction. The plain line represents basalt residual melt only. The dashed line integrates both residual and crustal melts.

4.4 Melt segregation

Residual and crustal melts are less dense than the surrounding crystals and are buoyant. Melt buoyant ascent through the deep hot zone and compaction of the

crystals have been modelled by Solano et al (2012). Compaction results in the formation of high porosity waves where melt concentrates. The continuous crystallisation of the melt during its ascent through the geotherm results in layers of melts with a rhyolitic composition. If the emplacement mode is favourable to crustal melting (over-accretion), the residual melt from the basalt cross the boundary between the intrusions and the country rock and ascent through the partially melted crust, making mixing between residual and crustal melts inevitable.

4.5 Case study: the generation of Snake River Plain Rhyolites, USA

The eastern Snake River Plain is associated with the Yellowstone hot spot track. Between 7000 and 10,000 km³ of metaluminous rhyolites have been erupted in Snake River Plain between 12.7 and 8.0 Ma (Bonnichsen et al, 2008) followed by intense basaltic volcanism. The erupted rhyolites were hot (900°C-1000°C), dry (no hydrous minerals) and crystal-poor (Leeman et al., 2008). The most popular hypothesis for their generation is partial melting of a crustal protolith consecutive to the emplacement of basalt. Low $\delta^{18}O$ indicate a contamination by surface water, which restricts the depth of melting to no more than 15 km.

I used numerical simulation to quantify the amount of basalt needed as a heat source to generate Snake River Plain rhyolites by partial melting of the crust. We assumed that caldera diameters (~100 km) reflect the melted area and that melt fraction of the protolith is ~25%, so that the crust must have been molten over a thickness of at least 3.6 km to produce the observed volume of erupted rhyolites. If the basalt complex is coherent and emplaced by over-accretion, very large volumes of basalts are needed, corresponding to a thickness of 16 km, to produce the required volume of crustal melts. This is more than twice the amount calculated with a basic energy balance calculation that ignores the way heat actually diffuses through the crust.

4.6 Conclusion

The case study of Snake River Plain illustrates the difficulty to generate large volumes of melt by partial melting of the crust at shallow depth where temperatures are cold. Crustal isotopic signatures are common in differentiated igneous rocks, but it is often difficult to determine precisely the relative importance of the crustal component relative to the mantle component because of a lack of information on the isotopic ratios of the protolith. The simulation of deep hot zones suggest that,

unless the crust is very fertile, differentiation of basalt plays a dominant role in the production of silicic melts.

A large diversity of melts are produced in deep hot zones contemporaneously and successively (Fig. 4.9). Mafic melts are present in recently emplaced basalt sills that are not yet thermally equilibrated with their surroundings. The residual melts in the partially molten mafic complex are more evolved and can be bimodal in compositions depending on the basalt H_2O content. Melt segregation produces layers of highly differentiated melts. If the crust is fertile enough and the sill emplacement mode is favourable, crustal melts are also present in the system. All these melt are susceptible to mix and produce intermediate compositions.

Figure 4.9: Melts presents in a deep hot zone include mafic melts in the recently emplaced basalt sills, residual melts in the mafic complex, whose composition depends on H_2O and on the temperatures of the hot zone, differentiated melts in segregated melt layers, and crustal melts.

Selected publications

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Chapter 5

Growth of magma bodies in the upper crust and plutonism-volcanism relationship

5.1 The generation of large magma chambers

The relationship between plutons and magma chamber is controversial (e.g. Glazner et al, 2004, Lipman, 2007) and there is no agreement on the shape and emplacement mechanism of igneous bodies in the upper crust. A series of magma bodies conceptual models are described in the literature (Fig. 5.1). Petrological models implicitly assume the presence of large magma tanks without considering how such large volumes of magma are emplaced in the upper crust (Bohrson and Spera, 2001, DePaolo, 1981). Theoretical and geophysical studies of magma chamber are generally based on a spherical or ellipsoidal geometry (e.g. Jellinek and DePaolo, 2003, Pinel and Jaupart, 2000). Diapiric ascent and emplacement of granitic magma resulting in vertically extended and deeply rooted plutons used to be a dominant model.

Implicit behind the models of large magma tanks and diapirs is the concept that plutons result from the solidification of large magma chambers. This concept has been seriously questioned by high precision geochronology that showed a several millions years difference in ages between different units within a pluton or batholith (Coleman et, 2004, Matzel et al., 2006). Because these age differences well exceed the cooling time of the volumes of magma these plutons correspond to, these data imply that the plutons were emplaced incrementally over protracted timescale. Therefore, the whole pluton was never in a magmatic state at the same time, which implies that magma chambers are much smaller than previously thought (Coleman et al, 2004, Glazner et al, 2004).

For mechanical and thermal reasons, magma ascent via propagating fractures, as dykes, is now considered more likely than diapirism even for silicic melts (Clemens and Mawer, 1992, Petford et al, 2000). A model that is supported by field observations (e.g. Michel et al, 2008), experimental studies (e.g. Kavanagh et al, 2006) and theory (e.g. Gudmundsson, 2011) involve dykes that turn into sills at the interface between two lithological layers or because of a change in stress orientations or country rock density (see sections 3.4 and 4.1). Larger igneous bodies result from the amalgamation of a series of these sills (Menand, 2008, de Saint Blanquat, 2011). In agreement with this model, geophysical studies show that granitoid plutons are either tabular or funnel-shaped (Cruden and McCaffrey, 2001).

Figure 5.1: Conceptual models of igneous bodies shape. a. Large magma tank. b. Spherical magma chamber. c. Diapirs. d. Series of dykes turning into sills to form a tabular igneous body. e. Series of dykes turning into sills to form a funnel-shaped igneous body

I numerically simulated the growth of a granodioritic pluton by the repeated addition of sills. I calculated the respective proportions of the pluton where: 1. Temperatures and melt fractions are high enough for the magma to be mobile and eruptible; 2. Melt is present within a crystalline framework and 3. The magma has totally solidified.

For magma to accumulate, the heat advected by each sill must be higher than the heat loss by conduction during the time interval between two sill injections. At the beginning of the intrusive sequence, the country rocks are cold and, unless the time interval between injections is very short, each sill solidifies before the next one is emplaced. As the system heats up, the heat loss between sill injections decreases. When temperatures are high enough, sills cease to solidify and a magma chamber starts growing. We call the time interval between the first sill and the accumulation

of magma, the incubation period. Michaut and Jaupart (2006) showed that the incubation time τ is a power function of the emplacement rate q :

$$\tau = \alpha q^{-2} \quad (5.1)$$

The emplacement rate q is the sills thickness divided by the time interval between two sills. It corresponds to velocity of sills accretion and body thickening. The parameter α depends on the magma and country rocks physical parameters, initial temperatures, and temperature-melt fraction relationships. α can be calculated with numerical simulation (Fig. 5.2). I found $\alpha \approx 155$ for a tonalite emplaced between 5 and 10 km depth (Annen, 2009, Annen, 2011).

Figure 5.2: The relationship between incubation times and emplacement for a granodioritic magma emplaced in the upper crust (roof at 5 km depth). The symbols are the result of numerical simulation. The simulations were run with sills radii of 5 and 10 km. The effect of sills radius r on the incubation time is weak.

Equation (5.1) is strictly valid for a 1D system. It is also a very good approximation for 3D systems (Fig. 5.2) although the incubation times are longer than predicted by equation (5.1) at very low emplacement rates. Indeed, for long time intervals between sills, a horizontal thermal gradient, in addition to the vertical thermal gradient, affects the temperature at the centre of the intrusion.

In a context of sills amalgamating to form an igneous body, a magma chamber grows only if the total emplacement duration of the igneous body is longer than the incubation time. Whereas the ability of the igneous body to host a magma chamber primarily depends on the emplacement rate, the volume of magma in the

system depends on both the emplacement rate and the area of the sills, i.e. on the volumetric flux. I found that to generate enough eruptible magma to feed a super eruption ($\gtrsim 450 \text{ km}^3$, Self, 2005), the volumetric flux must be of the order of 10^{-2} - $10^{-1} \text{ km}^3/\text{yr}$. Gelman et al (2013) found that by optimising all parameters and using a near eutectic temperature-melt fraction relationship, and a conductivity-temperature function that result in an insulating crust (Witthington et al, 2009), they could reduce this minimum flux to $3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ km}^3/\text{yr}$.

The average flux that build up plutons based on geochronological studies is a few 10^{-4} to a few $10^{-3} \text{ km}^3/\text{yr}$ (Crisp, 1984, Coleman et al 2004, Matzel et al 2006, Leuthold et al, 2012), thus many plutons were apparently emplaced too slowly to allow for the presence of a big magma chamber. This implies that the magma chambers that feed super eruption are more rare and transient than previously thought. It also implies that differentiation rarely happens in the upper crust on a pluton scale.

5.2 The effect of varying fluxes

The very existence of super eruptions and associated caldera collapses bears witness to the existence of large magma chambers and imply that magma can be injected with a flux that is superior to the flux recorded by U series in plutonic rocks. To reestablish the link between plutons and supereruptions, waxing and waning stages in magmatic cycles have been hypothesised with major eruptions happening during the acme of magmatic activity (Lipman, 2007).

The calculations described in the former section assume a constant flux of magma with a time interval between sill emplacements that does not vary over the igneous body emplacement duration. For her PhD research project, Anne Schöpa, tested the effect of flux variations. She based her simulations on the data available for the Tuolumne Intrusive Suite (Sierra Nevada, USA), where the long-term average flux inferred from zircon dating is $1.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ km}^3/\text{yr}$. She varied the flux while maintaining this long-term average flux, so that time of above-average fluxes are compensated by time of below-average fluxes. She found that monotonously increasing or decreasing flux over time was not resulting in the growth of large magma chambers disproving the hypothesis that super eruptions are the manifestation of an activity maximum in a waxing and waning magmatic system (Lipmann, 2007). Large magma chambers could be produced only with a step-like increase in magma fluxes of more than one order of magnitude. This result is supported by recent studies of crystal residence times that suggest that large volumes of magma are assembled very rapidly over timescales of only a few hundreds to a few thousands years before major eruptions (Druitt et al, 2012, Allan et al, 2013, Gualda et al, 2012).

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Chapter 6

Modelling magma chambers beneath Caribbean volcanoes

To get insight into the dynamics of magma chambers, models of incremental growth of a magma body were applied to two volcanic systems: Mt Pelée (Martinique) and Soufrière Hills (Montserrat). Both volcanoes are located in the lesser Antilles Arc (fig. 1.1 and 6.1). Mt Pelée last eruption was in 1929-1932 and the volcano is infamous for its 1902 pyroclastic flows that killed 29,000 people and destroyed the city of Saint-Pierre. Soufrière Hills is erupting since 1995 and drove a large proportion of Montserrat population to leave the Island. Plymouth, the capital city, has been engulfed by pyroclastic flows and lahars.

To model Mt Pelée magma chamber, I collaborated with Michel Pichavant from the *Institut des Sciences de la Terre d'Orléans*. The model is mostly constrained by petrological data (Annen et al., 2008b). Although petrology and geochronology were used to constrain the model of Soufrière Hills magma chamber, it is mostly based on geophysics (Annen et al., 2014) and results from a close collaboration with seismologists, in particular Michele Paulatto and Tim Minshull from the University of Southampton.

6.1 Mt Pelée, Martinique

Mt Pelée (Martinique Island) have erupted silicic andesite over the last 13,500 yrs without much variation in composition. This suggests that the magma chamber is in a steady state. Pre-eruptive temperatures of 875-900°C and pressures of 2 ± 0.5 kbar were determined with petrological experiments (Pichavant et al., 2002). The average erupted volume is 0.3 km^3 so we explored the conditions required to maintain a volume of 0.3 km^3 of magma at 875-900°C at a depth of about 7 km over 13,500 yrs. Different eruptive/intrusive ratio were tested, from a situation where

Figure 6.1: Location of Montserrat and Martinique in the lesser Antilles arc

all the intruded magma is eventually erupted so that no volume is added to the crust, to a situation where the quantity of erupted magma relative to the intrusive volumes is small enough to be neglected. The intermediate cases investigated are that half and one fifth of the intruded magma is eventually erupted. I tested the hypothesis that the chamber grows by addition of dykes or by addition of sills. In both cases, maintaining a magma chamber at 875°C requires a minimum emplacement rate q_{th} of a few centimetres per year.

The total volume of magma erupted over the last 13,500 yrs is about 10.2 km^3 , which correspond to an average eruptive flux Q_e of $7.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ km}^3/\text{yr}$. With this eruptive flux, we can calculate an intrusive emplacement rate q_v for each of our eruptive/intrusive ratio r and for a range of dyke or sill radius R :

$$q_v = \frac{Q_e}{\pi R^2} r \quad (6.1)$$

For a magma chamber to be permanent beneath Mt Pelée, this emplacement rate must be higher than the minimum emplacement rate q_{th} determined numeri-

cally:

$$q_v > q_{th} \quad (6.2)$$

We this constrain, and for eruptive/intrusive ratio of 1/5 to 1 we could put limit to the radius of the sheets to 1-5 km and emplacement rates to 4-50 cm/yr (Fig. 6.2). Because the emplacement rate is higher than the extension rate typical of arcs, it is more likely that the magma chamber grows by addition of sills rather than dykes unless the eruptive/intrusive ratio was very high.

Figure 6.2: These diagrams illustrate how equations (6.1) and (6.2) were used to constrain the sills emplacement rate and radius of a long-lived magma chamber at Mt Pelee. The extrusive/intrusive ratios are 1/2 (on left) and 1/5 (on right)

6.2 Soufrière Hills, Montserrat

A seismic tomography of the Island of Montserrat reveals a negative wave velocity anomaly beneath the active volcano of Soufrière Hills, which is not found beneath the other now extinct edifices (Paulatto et al., 2012). The depth of this anomaly corresponds to the depth at which the crystalline assemblage of the erupted products equilibrated and to the depth of surface deformation sources, which strongly suggest that it is caused by the presence of a magma chamber.

The temperatures required to account for the velocity anomaly are above the solidus of the andesite erupted by the volcano, which confirms the presence of melt. Inversion of seismic wave velocities produces melt fractions of 2 to 9% but does not account for the loss in signal due to limited seismic resolution (Paulatto et al., 2012). By modelling the temperatures and melt fractions in a magma

chamber, calculating the corresponding seismic waves velocities and smoothing the tomographic images to account for the information loss during data acquisition, we were able to reproduce the tomography with much higher melt fractions ($>30\%$) (Paulatto et al, 2012).

I ran a series of magma chamber growth simulations and tested a range of emplacement durations, magma chamber radii, and magma initial temperatures and melt fractions (Annen et al., 2014). We could fit the tomography with chamber radii from 2 to 5 km and emplacement durations from 6,000 to 150,000 yrs. Because of a trade off between radius and emplacement duration, the fluxes that build the igneous body hosting the magma chamber is limited to a range of 7×10^{-4} to $3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ km}^3/\text{yr}$.

Figure 6.3: Soufrière Hills magma reservoir simulation. The symbols show all the simulation runs. The coloured squares show the simulations where the tomography is reproduced. Contour lines are for fluxes labeled in \log_{10} of km^3/yr

Rare element diffusion profiles in zoned plagioclases erupted by Soufrière Hills are far from equilibrium and indicate a residence time in the magma of these crystals of less than 350 yrs (Zellmer et al., 2003). This residence time is much shorter than those predicted by the simulations. Our results can be reconciled with the residence times recorded by plagioclases if only the most recent batch of magma emplaced is erupted, which is more likely to happen if the rest of the magma body is a crystalline mush rather than an eruptible magma chamber. Producing a crystalline mush rather than an eruptible magma chamber and yet fitting the tomography anomaly require emplacement duration of 15,000-150,000 yrs and limit

fluxes to 7×10^{-4} - 2.4×10^{-3} km³/yr (Fig 6.4).

Figure 6.4: Same as figure 6.3, but the coloured squares show the simulations where the tomography is reproduced and the reservoir is a crystalline mush rather than a mobile magma chamber.

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Chapter 7

Emplacement dynamics of granitoid plutons

7.1 Emplacement of Manaslu leucogranites, Himalaya

The modelling of Manaslu leucogranite emplacement results from a collaboration with Bruno Scaillet from the *Institut des Sciences de la Terre d'Orléans*. The Manaslu is the best studied Himalayan leucogranite (Fig. 7.1). Leucogranites represent rare examples of silicic igneous rock that are not associated with mafic magmas and can be convincingly attributed to the anatexis of sedimentary crustal rocks in an orogenic context (Patiño Douce, 1999).

Our modelling of the Manaslu emplacement is based on the following observations:

1. Strong large-scale and medium-scale Rb/Sr heterogeneities within the pluton, that are believed to reflect the heterogeneity of the protolith (e.g. Deniel et al, 1987);
2. An upper thermal aureoles of less than 100 m thick, which is remarkably thin relative to the leucogranite thickness that is estimated to 5 km (Guillot et al., 1995).

We interpreted the Rb/Sr heterogeneity as a marker of the absence of large-scale convection that would produce internal magma mixing and homogenisation. Thus we explored pluton emplacement conditions that result in temperatures and melt fractions that are too low for the onset of convection over a scale that is larger than a single pulse. We calculated the Rayleigh number:

Figure 7.1: Generalized geological map of the Manaslu area in central Nepal, from Annen et al. (2006) after Colchen et al. (1986).

$$Ra = \frac{\rho g \alpha \Delta T w^3}{\mu \kappa} \quad (7.1)$$

with ΔT , the temperature gradient within a magma layer of thickness w , α the volumetric coefficient of thermal expansion, κ the thermal diffusivity and μ the magma viscosity.

The magma viscosity is a function of the melt viscosity μ_0 and crystal fraction ϕ (Roscoe, 1952):

$$\mu = \mu_0 \left(1 - \frac{\phi}{\phi_m}\right)^{-n} \quad (7.2)$$

ϕ_m is the critical crystal fraction beyond which the material stop behaving as a

fluid and n is a constant. Following Lejeune and Richet (1995), we used $\phi_m = 0.6$ and $n = 2.5$. Convection requires that the Rayleigh number exceed a critical value Ra_c . We chose a Ra_c of 3000 (Sparks et al, 1984).

I ran a series of leucogranite emplacement simulations with different emplacement rates and thermal conductivities and determined for each simulation the thickness of leucogranitic magma that can be emplaced before the Rayleigh number becomes critical and large-scale convection starts (Annen et al., 2006b, Annen and Scaillet, 2006). To build up the whole thickness of the Manaslu (~ 5 km) and keep temperatures and melt fractions low enough to avoid the onset of large-scale convection, the emplacement rate must be less than a few millimetres per year. This critical emplacement rate can be compared with those determined for the accumulation of eruptible granodioritic in the upper crust (see chapters 5 and 6), since both are related to the accumulation of mobile magma. The critical emplacement rate determined for the Manaslu leucogranites is one order of magnitude lower than those determined for granodioritic magma emplaced at 5 km depth. This difference is due to highest initial country rock temperature (300 °C) at the deeper level (12.5 km) of the Manaslu emplacement and to the lowest temperature at which the magma become locked (770°C) compared to cold initial temperatures of 150 °C and critical temperatures of 850-875 °C for the upper crustal magma chambers described in chapters 5 and 6.

As a further step, we simulated the leucogranite emplacement with contemporaneous surface denudation (Annen and Scaillet, 2006). An additional constrain is that the magma can not have crystallised at depth of less than 10 km because of the presence of muscovite in the crystalline assemblage. The leucogranite is emplaced by under-accretion (Fig.3.6), so that the sill intrusive level get deeper with time except if the denudation rate compensates for this effect. If denudation rate is fast relative to emplacement rate, crystallisation of the later sills is too shallow and muscovite cannot crystallise, however the emplacement rate itself is limited by the absence of convection. The simulations suggest that the denudation rate during the leucogranite emplacement did not exceed a few millimetres per year.

The other observation we used to quantify the emplacement rate of the Manaslu leucogranite is the thickness of its upper thermal aureole (Guillot et al, 1995). My calculations show that for a given total thickness of the intrusion (5 km in this case), the size of the thermal aureole is proportional to the emplacement rate except for very low emplacement rate where the aureole becomes independent of the emplacement rate (Fig. 7.2). Indeed, at very low emplacement rate, the country rock has time to cool down completely between magma pulses and the aureole size is controlled by the thickness of a single sill. The aureole limiting emplacement rate depends strongly on the country rock initial temperatures, hence on emplacement depth. According to the simulations, an aureole of 100 m can be

explained by emplacement rates inferior to 1 mm/yr, with initial country rock temperature of less than 300°C and magma pulses of 20 to 60 meters thick.

Figure 7.2: Relative size of the top and bottom thermal aureole induced by an igneous body incrementally emplaced by sills under-accretion as a function of the time interval between sills. The aureole size is normalized by the size the aureole associated with the same body instantaneously emplaced. Here the sill thickness is 100 m and the emplacement rate is 100 divided by the recurrence interval. For long recurrence intervals, i.e. low emplacement rates, the aureole size is independent from the body total size and is determined by the size of one increment.

Both aureole thickness and geochemical heterogeneities point to an emplacement rate of less than a few mm per yrs, which corresponds to emplacement durations of more than 5 My. This duration is close to the duration based on geochronological ages difference between the top and bottom of the leugranite (Harrison et al., 1999).

7.2 Emplacement of Lago della Vacca granitoid complex, Italian Alps

The Lago della Vacca complex is a 15 km² granitoid intrusion that is part of the Adamello intrusive suite in the Italian Alps. Crystal fabrics measured by John and Blundy (1993) and by Schöpa et al (in preparation) as well as AMS (Anisotropy

of Magnetic Susceptibility) fabrics (Schöpa et al, in preparation) show steeply dipping foliations forming an ellipsoidal concentric pattern around a focus point located at the North-West of the complex (fig. 7.3). This Northwest part of the complex is the only one where lineation dominates over foliation. The foliation is believed to be due to flattening of early emplaced magma by magma forcefully injected afterwards with the North-West part being emplaced last. It is difficult to distinguish on the basis of the fabric between emplacement by ballooning with a dominant horizontal displacement component (John and Blundy, 1993) or by stacking of steeply dipping sheets.

Figure 7.3: Foliation from Anisotropy of Magnetic Susceptibility in pluton Lago della Vacca. Schöpa et al, in preparation.

The hypothesis of the Lago della Vacca magma emplacing as a horizontally expanding balloon was adopted to investigate the emplacement rate of the pluton (Caricchi et al, 2012). Variations in the degree of deformation of mafic enclaves were used to constrain the models. For mafic enclaves to be able to deform, their viscosity must be similar to the viscosity of the granodioritic host magma. This happens only at temperatures close to the granodiorite liquidus and solidus temperature. Between those temperatures, the mafic enclaves are more viscous than their host and are transported as rigid objects.

I developed codes to calculate temperatures and melt fractions in a cylindrical magmatic body expanding horizontally. The shape of enclaves were determined from the relative melt fractions and viscosities of enclaves and host magma and from their trajectory during the pluton growth. The model results that best fit

Lago della Vacca enclave shape distributions were obtained for pluton emplacement durations of 50 to 150 kyr in agreement with zircon ages (Schoene et al, 2012).

Selected publications

Annen, C., Scaillet, B. and Sparks, R.S.J., 2006. Thermal Constraints on the Emplacement Rate of a Large Intrusive Complex: The Manaslu Leucogranite, Nepal Himalaya. *J. Petrol.*, 47(1): 71-95.

Annen, C. and Scaillet, B., 2006. Thermal evolution of leucogranites in extensional faults: Implications for Miocene denudation rates in the Himalayas. In: R.D. Law, M.P. Searle and L. Godin (Editors), *Channel Flow, Ductile Extrusion and Exhumation of lower-mid crust in Continental Collision Zones*. Special Publications. Geological Society, London, pp. 309-326.

Caricchi, L., Annen, C., Rust, A. and Blundy, J., 2012. Insights into the mechanisms and timescales of pluton assembly from deformation patterns of mafic enclaves. *Journal of Geophysical Research-Solid Earth*, 117.

Chapter 8

Work in progress and proposals

8.1 Work in progress

Work in progress involves applications of thermal models to investigate the emplacement of the Yerington batholith in Nevada and of two granitoid bodies in Italy: Mt Capanne pluton on Elba Island and the Bergell intrusion in the Alps. For the Yerington batholith, Anne Schöpa is doing the modelling and we are collaborating with John Dilles, an expert in the geology of Yerington, and with Steve Spark and Jon Blundy. Field work and zircons analysis are done by postdoctoral researcher Mélanie Barboni on Elba Island and by PhD student Kyle Samperton on Bergell intrusion. Both are supervised by Blair Schoene who is an expert in high precision geochronology.

8.1.1 Modelling Yerington batholith, Nevada, USA: insight into the genesis of porphyry copper deposits (Funded by BHP Billiton)

This small project is developed within the framework of a larger project funded by BHP Billiton to investigate the link between volcanism, tectonic and ore mineralisation. Porphyry Copper deposits are associated with magmatic intrusions, which provide the volatiles that transport minerals. Modelling the emplacement of igneous bodies associated with ore deposits is expected to provide insights in the mechanism of mineralisation. Indeed, the emplacement rate of igneous bodies controls their thermal evolution and crystallisation. In turn, crystallisation results in volatile exsolution. Thus the rate of volatiles exsolution, potentially associated with mineralisation, depends on the rate of magma emplacement.

We are currently modelling the emplacement of the Yerington batholith, which has been tilted and is now exposed from roof to floor at paleodepth of 1 to 6 km

(Dilles and Profett, 1995). The Yerington batholith is composed of three major intrusions: McLeod Hill quartz monzodiorite, Bear quartz monzonite and Luhr Hill granite. A series of granite porphyry dykes are sourced in the Luhr Hill granite and are associated with copper mineralisation. Mc Leod Hill, Bear Hill and Luhr Hill were modelled as series of sills, with longer period of repose marking the transition from one unit to the other. Because field evidences suggest that melt remained in the system between each unit, we looked for emplacement rates and repose period that satisfy this condition. An emplacement rate of 4 cm/yr for each unit, with a repose period of 100 kyr between units allow for the production of large volumes of melts and is reasonable in terms of the deformation the crust can sustain. At this rate, the whole batholith can be emplaced in 1 My, in agreement with geochronological data (Dilles and Wright, 1988).

In terms of water exsolution, we predict an episode of exsolution at the beginning of each unit emplacement, when the system is relatively cold and sills solidify. At a later stage, when temperatures are high and magma accumulates, volatiles remain dissolved in the melt. A second exsolution episode takes place after injection ceases and the magma cools down.

8.1.2 Modelling Mt Capanne pluton, Elba Island, Italy

The Elba intrusive suite is composed of a Christmas tree laccoliths and of a pluton, Mt Capanne (Farina et al, 2010, Rocchi et al, 2010), itself formed by sub-horizontal sheets (Fig. 8.1). From top to bottom, three units have been identified in Mt. Capanne, based on rock textures and chemistry: Sant'Andrea (250 m thick, based on outcrops), San Francesco (650 m thick, based on outcrops) and San Piero (1500 m thick, based on geophysics). Mélanie Barboni has obtained high precision zircon ages on two samples for each Mt Capanne unit. For each hand sample, the range of zircon ages covers several hundred thousand years. Similarly large wide ranges of age have been found in Adamello (Schoene et al, 2012). Schoene et al (2012) proposed that only the youngest zircons date the granite emplacement and that sample age spans correspond to zircon residence time at a deeper level. Mt Capanne is an ideal site to test this hypothesis because of good constrains on the depth and thickness of the granitoid. I will calculate the solidification time for each unit of Mt Capanne. If the solidification time is shorter than the age span, it will confirm that the zircon ages were not acquired at emplacement level. This is of fundamental importance for the interpretation of zircon ages in general.

Assuming that emplacement ages are given by the youngest zircons, we can infer the rate at which Mt Capanne was emplaced. This rate appears to be fluctuating. I will simulate the emplacement of Mt Capanne at these rates and determine the size of any magma chamber. This will tell us if Mt Capanne could have fed volcanic eruptions and will provide us with further insight on the plutonism-volcanism

relationship.

Figure 8.1: Geological map of Elba Island and Mt Capanne. From Barboni and Schoene (2014).

8.1.3 Modelling Bergell intrusion, Italian Alps (NSF funded)

Most of this section summarises the NSF grant proposal of Blair Schoene. As Mt Capanne, the Bergell intrusion has exceptional outcrop conditions although on a much larger scale (Fig. 8.2). Both roof and floor are exposed at corresponding paleodepths of 12 and 20 km respectively. The Bergell intrusion is a normally zoned intrusion with minor gabbros at the margin, a thick outer rim of tonalites, and granodiorites at the core (Berger and Gieré, 1995, Davidson et al, 1996). It is interpreted as a nested 10 km in diameter diapir that intruded the crust over 5-6 Ma (Berger et al, 1996 and Rosenberg, 1995). An alternative interpretation is that of an intrusion emplaced incrementally by addition of sheets. Those hypotheses are tested by PI Blair Schoene and PhD student Kyle Samperton with detailed field works and rock dating. If the diapir hypothesis is true the rocks should become younger towards the core of the intrusion. If the sheet hypothesis is correct, ages repartition are expected to be either random or to progress in age from top to

bottom or bottom to top depending on the emplacement mode (Random, under or over-accretion).

Figure 8.2: a. Simplified geological map of Bergell intrusion from Berger et al. (1996). Green dashed line show the extent of the thermal aureole. Green numbers are pressure estimates. b. Diapiric emplacement hypothesis. c. Incremental sheets emplacement hypothesis. Figure courtesy of Kyle Samperton and Blair Schoene.

My contribution to this project is to provide the codes to model the emplacement of Bergell intrusion with the geochronological data as a basis. It will be the first time that a large intrusion will be modelled with such detailed geochronological constrains. With the simulations, we will estimate temperatures and melt content during the emplacement of the pluton and determine 1) if the granodiorite can be the product from in-situ differentiation of the tonalite, 2) if the whole of the granodiorite can have been partially molten at some point in time, 3) the rheological state of the country rock. All those information are relevant to validate or invalidate the hypothesis of a diapiric emplacement.

8.2 Proposals

In the next sections, I will summarise two proposals that are currently under evaluation by a funding body. One of this proposal is basic science and is aimed at determining the role stress field evolution in the construction of large igneous bodies. The other one is focused on Soufrière Hills and its objective is to image the whole magma plumbing system, from mantle to crust, that sits beneath the volcano.

8.2.1 Thermo-mechanical modelling of igneous body growth (NERC standard grant proposal, in review)

The models of igneous bodies emplacement I developed during the last decade show that the way magma is emplaced exerts a major control on its thermal evolution. Two parameters are of primary importance: the emplacement rate and the intrusions geometry. The new frontier is to determine what these emplacement rates and intrusion geometries are in nature and to establish the mechanisms that control them. We know that high fluxes of 10^{-2} - 10^{-1} km³/yr are needed to build up the largest magma chambers (Annen, 2009). We also know that magma fluxes are likely to be highly variable in time (Pelletier, 1999, Schöpa and Annen, 2013, Annen et al, in preparation). Establishing the conditions that cause magma high fluxes has implication for our appreciation of the major volcanic hazard that large eruptions represent. Our objective is to understand how and why the growth rate of igneous bodies varies and what the conditions are for the existence of large magma chambers.

Magma fluxes and flux variations are probably modulated at different levels in the crust by a range of processes: 1) At the source, where melt is generated and extracted; 2) During transport, where feeder dykes need to be able to propagate and reach a growing igneous body; 3) By the interaction between several magma chambers located at different depths within the crust. In this proposal, we focus on processes 2 and 3. Addressing process 1 will be the focus of future work.

Pinel and Jaupart (2000) showed that the stress induced by the load of a volcanic edifice can arrest vertical dyke propagation. We will test if the stress related to the growth of an igneous body can have a similar effect. We propose to explore experimentally and numerically the interactions and possible feedback effects between dyke propagation, igneous body growth and the crustal stress field. We expect this evolving stress field to influence dyke propagation in two main ways: 1) By modifying dyke trajectories (Karlstrom et al, 2009), or 2) By stopping their upward propagation if either the dyke internal pressure cannot overcome the external stress (Pinel and Jaupart, 2000) or the dyke thickness is reduced to such an extent that the magma cools and solidifies. We expect that as the igneous body grows and the stress increases, dykes tend to be focused towards the body, but they also tend to stop en route. Even if the number and volume of dykes that are injected from the source remains constant, we expect the number of dykes able to reach and add volume to the igneous body to vary over time.

This a joint proposal between University of Bristol and University of Liverpool. I am the lead PI and Janine Kavanagh is PI at Liverpool. We will use two methods to reach our objectives: Numerical and experimental modelling.

I will lead the numerical part of the project. I will use Comsol to compute the stress induced by feeder dykes and by a growing igneous body. Successive

dykes dimensions and orientation and their ability to reach and feed the igneous body will be calculated as a function of the evolving stress. Heat transfer will be computed and the effect of temperature on the crust mechanical properties will be taken into account. We will also consider the possible mechanical interactions between several growing igneous bodies.

Janine Kavanagh will lead the experimental part of the project. The experiments involve the injection of a fluid in a tank filled with gelatine. The gelatine has visco-elastic properties and is an analogue for the crust. The injected fluid is an analogue for magma. The technique of Particle Image Velocimetry will be used to image and quantify deformation in the gelatine. Davis Dennis, an expert in Particle Image Velocimetry, is co-Investigator. Virginie Pinel (IRD, ISTERre, Chambéry), Thierry Menand (IRD-USP, Laboratoire Volcans et Magma, Clermont-Ferrand) and Michel de Saint-Blanquat (CNRS, Observatoire Midi-Pyrénées, Toulouse) are project partners.

8.2.2 Imaging the crustal magma plumbing systems of Soufrière Hills volcano, Montserrat (ERC advanced grant proposal, in review)

This proposal build upon the SEA CALIPSO tomographic experiment that resulted in imaging the upper part of Soufrière Hills shallow magma chamber (Paulatto et al, 2012) and allowed us to estimate the magma fluxes beneath the volcano (Annen et al., 2014). The objective of the proposal is to acquire new seismic data and image Soufrière Hills plumbing system from the base of the crust to the surface.

High precision tomography will be obtained by using 3D full-wavefield inversion. The wave velocity data will be used to build up an integrated model of the intrusive system. The objective is to determine the number of distinct magma chambers and melt reservoirs and their dimensions, and to estimate the magma fluxes between those reservoirs. Geodetic data, corroborated by petrological data indicate the presence of magma at about 6 and 12 km depth. We will try to detect the presence of a deep hot zone and establish if there are two distinct reservoirs at 6 and 12 km linked by a conduit or if the system consists in a mush and is continuously molten between 6 and 12 km and possibly down to the deep hot zone.

The grant PI is Tim Minshull (University of Southampton). I will be responsible for the direct modelling of the magmatic system dynamics and for exploring the conditions in terms of heat flux and mass transfer that can result in the seismic observations. The method used in Annen et al (2014) will be developed by using a Monte Carlo approach and by expressing results in probabilistic terms. We will also integrate melt migrations to the simulation (Solano et al, 2012) and determine

if and where differentiation by compaction plays a role. Tim Henstock (University of Southampton) will lead the seismic data acquisition. Joanna Morgan (Imperial College) will be responsible for the full waveform inversion. Michele Paulatto (Goazur, France), Matthew Jackson (Imperial College) and Steve Sparks (University of Bristol) will be project partners and will contribute with their expertise.

Chapter 9

Conclusions

Numerical simulations that integrate data from petrology and geophysics proved a powerful tool to improve our understanding of magmatic processes. We learned from these simulations that endogenous growth shapes basaltic volcanic edifices, that many plutons never were large magma chambers and that crust melting at the contact with basalt is limited in case of amphibolitic or granulitic crusts. On the basis of physical constrains and petrological data, we were able to propose the conceptual model of deep hot zones where magmas acquire most of their compositional diversity before rapidly ascending and crystallising in the upper crust.

Magma chambers used to be modelled as large coherent bodies of instantaneously emplaced magma. Taking into account the fact that most igneous bodies are incrementally emplaced results in models that are more realistic but also more complex. We found that an igneous body thermal impact on its host rocks in terms of thermal aureoles and anatexis depends strongly on the emplacement geometry (Annen, 2011). Most importantly, we established how the thermal evolution of an igneous body depends on its emplacement rate. Those findings have major implications for the plutonic-volcanic relationship and for the generation of porphyry copper ore deposits.

Heat transfer calculation indicates that a large range of magma input rates are constructing igneous bodies. For the Manaslu leucogranite, magma was emplaced at a rate of a few mm per year or less and was unable to convect and to thermally imprint the country rock, whereas beneath Caribbean volcanoes, magma emplacement rate must have been at least one order of magnitude larger to account for the presence of shallow magma chambers. Finally, large caldera-forming magma chamber that feed ignimbrite eruptions require magma fluxes that are exceptionally high in comparison to those needed to grow smaller chambers typical of arc stratovolcanoes or to those typical of most plutons.

We have now to consider several timescales in the evolution of a magmatic system: the timescale of individual pulses, the timescale of the whole body and

intermediate timescales linked to magma flux variations. Evaluation of pluton emplacement timescales and magma chamber lifetimes often rely on zircon ages. Our current work on Mt Capanne and Bergell intrusions that integrate high precision zircon chronometry and heat transfer calculations put to the test the hypothesis that zircon ages date magma emplacement.

The work presented in this thesis leads to several new avenues for research as many questions remain open. For example, why are crustal signatures so common in igneous rocks when heat transfer calculations show that, except for very fertile protoliths, silicic melt generation is dominated by crystallisation of basalt? How variable are magma fluxes? How are these fluxes and their variations controlled? What are the size and geometry of magma increments and how are they controlled? Why are contacts between increments elusive in the largest intrusive bodies?

There is a wide range of potential developments for the models. To explore further crustal melting, future simulations could include H_2O transfer between the crystallising basalt and the crust, and the mechanical incorporation of crustal elements in magmas. Integrating in the simulations the computation of trace elements and isotopic ratios would provide means of comparison with natural rocks.

Potential lines of inquiry include, but are not limited to, the role of stress in the emplacement dynamics of magma bodies, the timescales of magma segregation and extraction in deep sources and their role in defining magmatic pulsatory behaviours, the modelling of texture at the contact between magma increments, or the link between long-term magma bodies evolution and geophysical signals recorded in volcanic areas.

Selected publication

Annen, C., 2011. Implications of incremental emplacement of magma bodies for magma differentiation, thermal aureole dimensions and plutonism-volcanism relationships. *Tectonophysics*, 500(1-4): 3-10.

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